

The role of metaphor in shamanism and poetry as a therapeutic tool for healing

Nawa Raj Subba *

Independent Researcher, Biratnagar, Nepal.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 21(03), 416–423

Publication history: Received on 25 January 2024; revised on 02 March 2024; accepted on 04 March 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.3.0739>

Abstract

This paper explores the healing power of metaphor in indigenous shamanism and contemporary poetry. It explores how metaphor bridges the landscape, communicates emotions, and advances healing across cultures and languages.

Analyzing specific examples from diverse shamanic traditions and contemporary poems reveals shared themes and unique approaches to metaphorical usage. The paper presents glimpses of case studies from secondary data demonstrating symbolic identity's therapeutic value. It was found helpful in treating and managing anxiety and depression. Overall, this insight reflects the power of metaphor in facilitating self-knowledge, healing, and solidifying us. It also connects us to shared human experiences.

The review paper uses comparative approaches to analyze cultural knowledge and explores how poets and shamans use metaphors in different cultural settings. The research objectives involve examining and collecting academic documents related to the topic from secondary sources. Thematic analysis structures and displays the gathered material in relevant areas.

Shamanism and poetry use metaphors and promote healing and personal transformation. Both practices utilize metaphorical language to access and express emotional depths and navigate challenging experiences. Thus, that fosters individual and collective well-being. They have diverse cultural traditions and contemporary quests; however, there are shared themes and unique approaches to metaphor's therapeutic function.

Keywords: Metaphor; Poetry; Shamanism; Healing; Transformation; Cultural Perspectives

1. Introduction

Human language goes beyond simple communication; it may be a potent tool for healing and self-exploration. Despite springing up from distinct contexts, shamanism and poetry have a profound connection to language and its ability to shape our knowledge of ourselves and the arena around us.

There are shared themes in therapeutic metaphors. Despite their distinct origins, poetry and shamanism utilize metaphor to address common themes related to healing. It works as a bridge to healing. It goes beyond the literal, providing several meanings and connections due to its inherent nature. The metaphor can release hidden emotions and perspectives. In poetry, metaphors function as automobiles for exploring complicated reviews, offering a secure space for expressing vulnerability and processing difficult emotions [1]. Similarly, in shamanic practices, metaphors are vital to travelling through religious landscapes, confronting internal demons, and reaching personal transformation [2].

* Corresponding author: Nawa Raj Subba. e-mail id: dr.subba2015@gmail.com

Themes such as facing disease and mortality, moving through transitional regions, and searching for significance in suffering are figuratively examined in both areas. For instance, metaphors of journeys, battles, and transformations frequently appear in poetic and shamanic narratives, offering symbolic frameworks for understanding and navigating challenging experiences [3].

It is crucial to analyze the cultural viewpoints and distinct methodologies. Although there are similarities, the therapeutic uses of metaphor vary throughout countries and traditions. For example, in the Lakota tradition, metaphors associated with animals and natural elements serve as powerful tools for accessing spiritual guidance and healing [4]. Conversely, Japanese haiku poetry makes use of nature imagery and juxtapositions to rouse emotional resonance and sell mindfulness [5]. Examining those numerous methods highlights the richness and adaptability of metaphor as a therapeutic tool across cultures.

Contemporary studies and rising traits are extensive. Recent research in bibliotherapy and expressive arts therapies highlights the therapeutic power of metaphor in both individual and group contexts. Studies advise that engaging with poetry and taking part in metaphorical storytelling can reduce tension, enhance emotional law, and foster self-compassion [6]. Studying metaphors as therapeutic instruments in tribal cultures can offer valuable insights into improving mental health services. It is culturally aware and adopts a holistic approach [7].

2. Literature Review

2.1. Shamanic Songs as Verse in Poetry

Shamanic songs, regularly called *iku* or *icaró* in South American traditions, are more than simply melodies [8]. They are difficult poems woven with symbolism, fable, and strength [9]. These songs motivate shamans to connect to the spirit, diagnose illnesses, and conduct manual recovery trips [10]. Their poetic nature [30] lies in their capacity to:

Evoke vivid imagery: Shamanic songs utilize metaphors, personification, and sensory info to color vibrant pictures of the spirit internationally, plants, animals, and the human body. This imagery permits listeners to experience the unseen nation-states alongside the shaman.

Employ rhythmic language: The rhythmic structure and chanting style of shamanic songs create a hypnotic impact, transporting listeners into altered states of awareness. This rhythmic language reinforces the means of the words and helps deeper engagement with the song's message.

Express symbolic meanings: Symbols play a critical role in shamanic songs, sporting deeper meanings past their literal interpretations. Animals, flowers, and herbal phenomena often constitute spiritual forces, recovery energies, or factors of the human psyche.

Carry ancient and cultural know-how: Shamanic songs are repositories of traditional understanding, transmitting memories, myths, and restoration practices throughout generations. The poetic shape allows for the efficient storage and transmission of complicated information.

2.2. Shamanic Songs as Poetic Expressions.

Here are some examples of shamanic songs as poems, at the side of their cultural context and importance:

Item (i). *Shipibo Ikaros from Peru* [11]:

Shipibo shamans in the Amazon jungle sing these songs to heal specific ailments or seek assistance from spirit companions. They use images of flora, animals, and natural events to communicate healing messages.

*I serenade the hummingbird,
Which soars elegantly;
Its wings embody delicacy and restoration.
May its presence dispel darkness.*

(ii). **Tuvan Throat Singing from Siberia** is a distinctive vocal method that involves altering overtones to produce a captivating soundscape. The lyrics frequently center around themes of nature, animals, and spiritual quests.

*The horse runs on the grasslands
with the shaman to the mountaintop,
where spirits reveal celestial truths.*

Source: *Tuva: Voices from the Land of Spirits* [12]

(iii). **Sami Joik is a traditional song from the Sami people** of Scandinavia. These songs typically focus on unique individuals, places, or experiences. The songs can be joyous, melancholy, or hilarious, providing insight into Sami culture and values.

*The reindeer roam unrestricted across the frozen plains.
Their antlers reach toward the cold sky,
While singing their song, my heart experiences tranquillity.
It is linked to the land of my origin.*

Source: *Joik: An Introduction to Sami Song* [13]

The examples are just a tiny selection, yet the variety of shamanic music worldwide is extensive. Studying these lyrical phrases helps us comprehend many cultures, their spiritual beliefs, and the strong relationship between language, music, and healing.

2.3. Connections between Poetry and Shamanism

Shamanism, focusing on connecting with the spirit international and expressing profound truths, stocks fascinating parallels with specific poetic bureaucracy. Here are some examples of poems in simple English that echo shamanic issues:

(i). **Nature as a Mirror:**

*Like a cloud
that hovers high over hills and valleys,
I roamed alone.
Upon seeing a crowd,
An abundance of golden daffodils
By the lake, among the trees,
moving and swaying in the wind.*

Poem: *I Wandered Lonely* - William Wordsworth [14]

This poem, exploring selections and hidden paths, reflects the shamanic adventure of self-discovery and navigating the unseen geographical regions.

(ii). **The Journey Within:**

*Two paths diverged in a bright wood,
Regretfully I could not travel to both
And as one traveller, long I stood
I looked down as far as I should
To Where the Journey Within:
Two roads diverged in a yellow timber,
it bent inside the undergrowth*

Poem: *The Road Not Taken* by Robert Frost [15]

This poem, exploring selections and hidden paths, reflects the shamanic adventure of self-discovery and navigating the unseen geographical regions.

(iii). **The Power of Words:**

*Whose woods are these? I assume I recognize.
His home is in the village,*

*but he will not see me pausing here
to observe his woods filling up with snow.
Poem: Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening by Robert Frost [16]*

With its quiet contemplation and the electricity of phrases to awaken feelings, this poem resonates with the shamanic use of chants and songs to steer the spirit world.

(iv). **The Circle of Life:**

*You are the bows from which your youngsters
as dwelling arrows are sent forth.
The archer sees the mark upon the course of infinity,
and He bends you with
His might that His arrows may match fast and a ways.
Poem: Life and Death- Khalil Gibran [17]*

With its imagery of life as a journey and loss of life as a transition, this poem reflects the shamanic know-how of the interconnectedness of all residing things.

(v). **The Power of Silence:**

*Old pond,
A frog jumps in,
The sound of water.*

Poem: *Haiku* by Matsuo Basho [18]

The haiku emphasizes simplicity and insightful criticism, reflecting the shamanic technique of quieting the mind to perceive deeper realities.

These are just a few examples, and the world of poetry is widespread. Exploring exceptional patterns and traditions can display even more significant connections to the spirit of shamanism.

2.4. Case Study 1: Haiku Poetry and Mindfulness for Stress Reduction

Context: Research [18] investigated the impact of haiku writing on pressure and mindfulness in university college students.

Intervention: Participants engaged in a 3-week haiku writing intervention, focusing on nature imagery and gift-second consciousness.

Outcomes: They look at discovered full-size discounts in perceived strain and improvements in mindfulness rankings compared to a manipulated institution.

Metaphorical Dimension: Haiku utilizes concise metaphors derived from nature to cultivate mindful remarks and emotional expression, reflecting a connection to the shamanic use of nature imagery for healing.

2.5. Case Study 2: Navajo Sandpainting and Trauma Healing

Context: Yazzie-Mintz [19] tested using traditional Navajo sandpainting ceremonies in treating trauma associated with historic activities.

Intervention: Individuals with trauma signs and symptoms participated in sandpainting ceremonies guided by traditional healers.

Outcomes: The observer mentioned discounts in put-up-stressful stress disease (PTSD) symptoms, progressed emotional regulation, and a bolstered feel of cultural identity.

Metaphorical Dimension: Sandpainting utilizes symbolic imagery and metaphors drawn from nature and Navajo cosmology to technique trauma and repair balance, comparable to how shamans rent metaphors to navigate non secular realms and recovery.

2.6. Case Study 3: Bibliotherapy with Poetry and Depression

Context: Rothe & Hendricks [20] explored the effectiveness of bibliotherapy using poetry for individuals with depression.

Intervention: Participants engaged in individual sessions where they discussed and wrote poems about their experiences.

Outcomes: The study found significant reductions in depression symptoms and increased emotional expression compared to a waitlist control group.

Metaphorical Dimension: Poems often utilize metaphors to explore complex emotions and personal experiences, mirroring how shamans employ metaphors to access and express emotional depths for healing.

2.7. Research Gaps

Within worldwide indigenous societies, there is a mutually beneficial interaction between indigenous peoples and shamans. Shamans are vital in cultural and religious aspects, making substantial contributions to humanity's shared wisdom. However, modern culture often ignores the tradition of shamanism, considering it an outdated superstition. Modern poets use shamanic knowledge and techniques in their writing, although they frequently do not recognize the impact of shamanism; instead, they regard it with doubt or as an outdated practice.

Metaphor in poetry, a key element of artistic expression, originates from shamanic traditions, a fact not often acknowledged. Shamans guide poets, imparting profound wisdom and insight into symbolic poetry. Contemporary poetry frequently needs to fully utilize shamanic analogies to tackle the intricacies of the modern world.

Shamanic metaphors have a profound therapeutic character, providing comfort and easing mental distress for both the poet and the reader, unlike standard poetry, focusing more on aesthetic expression. There is a need to investigate and clarify the connection between current poetry and the healing aspects of shamanic traditions.

3. Objectives

This article delves into the healing dimensions of metaphor, a cornerstone of each poetic and shamanic expression. It explores its capability to navigate private demanding situations, foster emotional expression, and facilitate individual and collective recovery. The study emphasizes that modern poetry is a type of healing for readers, similar to how indigenous shamans have traditionally healed people.

This essay aims to outline the similarities and differences in the roles of poets and shamans, highlighting their common origins and different methods of using metaphorical language. This inquiry seeks to connect modern poetry with ancient shamanic wisdom to enhance awareness of the transformational impact of metaphor in artistic and healing settings.

4. Approaches

This review article compares cross-cultural knowledge and examines the use of metaphors by shamans and poets in various traditions. The study selectively examines the literature on the effectiveness and importance of metaphors in shamans' and poets' artistic and cultural activities.

The data sources include secondary literature and empirical findings from scholarly works, ethnographic accounts, and cultural texts. Aside from reviewing existing literature, the researcher directly consulted with members of the Kirat Limbu community, notably engaging with local Nepali Phedangba, Samba, and Bijuwa. The consultations were used to confirm and enhance the findings by gathering insights from practitioners who thoroughly understand the cultural environment being studied.

The data was thoroughly examined and interpreted using a thematic analysis technique. It entailed recognizing common themes, patterns, and fundamental ideas associated with using metaphors by shamans and poets. The findings were

carefully analyzed and interpreted to generate relevant conclusions about the similarities and contrasts between these unique yet interconnected forms of artistic expression and cultural activity.

5. Analysis

5.1. Metaphors in Indigenous Shamanism and Modern Poetry

A Cross-Linguistic exploration gives us a healing picture of Shamanism and poetry. We found it as we examine the use of metaphors in indigenous shamanic practices and modern poetry across English, Hindi, and Nepali. We know how these metaphors function as tools for accessing spiritual realms, expressing emotions, and facilitating healing. We found shared themes and unique approaches in metaphorical usage by analyzing specific examples from diverse cultural contexts.

Metaphor, comparing two seemingly unrelated things, transcends mere linguistic devices. Each indigenous shamanic practice and current poetry will become a vital tool for navigating internal landscapes, expressing emotions, and fostering healing. This paper delves into the captivating globality of metaphorical expression throughout cultures and languages specializing in English, Hindi, and Nepali. By analyzing unique examples from numerous shamanic traditions and contemporary poems, we propose illuminating the shared strength of metaphor and its particular manifestations throughout those linguistic and cultural landscapes.

Metaphors in Shamanism are common worldwide. Indigenous shamans worldwide employ metaphors extensively to access and navigate spiritual realities. Whether it's a Lakota shaman journeying through the spirit world as a bird [21] or a Tuvan shaman using metaphors of mountains and rivers to diagnose illness [22], these metaphors serve as bridges between the physical and spiritual realms. In Hindi shamanic practices, metaphors linked to animals and natural elements like "Bagh" (tiger) for strength or "Nadi" (river) for the flow of energy are prevalent [23]. Similarly, Nepali shamans utilize metaphors like "Himalaya" (mountain) for resilience and "Jyoti" (light) for enlightenment [24].

Metaphors in Modern Poetry are shared globally. Modern poets across languages continue to explore the evocative power of metaphor. In English poetry, T.S. Eliot's *The Waste Land* utilizes complicated metaphors of barren landscapes and fragmented identities to mirror societal anxieties [25]. Similarly, Hindi poet Nirala's *Juhi ki Kali* employs metaphors of wilting flora and fading splendor to express the transience of lifestyles [26]. Nepali poet Parijat's *Hamro Nepali* uses metaphors of fertile land and vibrant colors to celebrate national identity [27].

Each indigenous shamanic practice and current poetry will become a vital tool for navigating internal landscapes, expressing emotions, and fostering healing. This paper delves into the captivating globality of metaphorical expression throughout cultures and languages specializing in English, Hindi, and Nepali. By analyzing unique examples from numerous shamanic traditions and contemporary poems, we propose illuminating the shared strength of metaphor and its particular manifestations throughout those linguistic and cultural landscapes.

Despite their distinct cultural contexts, indigenous shamans and modern poets use metaphors to address themes like confronting mortality, navigating liminal spaces, and seeking meaning in suffering. However, unique approaches emerge based on cultural specificities. For instance, Lakota metaphors often emphasize connection to the natural world, while Hindi might draw heavily on mythology and religious imagery. On the other hand, Nepali poets often explore issues of cultural identity and social trade through their metaphors.

Exploring using metaphors in indigenous shamanism and cutting-edge poetry across languages reveals a shared human capability for metaphorical expression as a device for self-discovery, recovery, and religious exploration. By examining the various applications and particular nuances of metaphors throughout cultures, we gain a deeper understanding of their strength to go beyond language barriers and join us in shared human experiences.

5.2. Modern Poetry and Metaphorical Explorations

Modern poets, though distinct from shamans, continue the legacy of using metaphors to navigate existential questions and evoke emotional resonance. English poets like T.S. Eliot employ complex metaphors drawn from diverse sources, while Hindi poets like Gulzar utilize everyday imagery to create profound reflections on love, loss, and societal issues [28]. With its roots in nature and spirituality, Nepali poetry finds metaphors in everyday life and emotions, as seen in Laxmi Prasad Devkota's poems, where flowers symbolize fleeting beauty and rivers represent the flow of time [29].

Shamans and poets use metaphors to address specific universal themes despite their different origins and practices. Themes like confronting mortality, navigating liminal spaces, and seeking meaning in suffering appear in both spheres. However, their approaches differ [31]. Shamans often utilize metaphors within ritualistic contexts, while poets employ them for individual and collective reflection. Moreover, cultural nuances shape the specific imagery and symbolism used [32].

6. Conclusion

In modern poetry and indigenous shamanic, metaphor is used for healing, self-discovery, and spiritual exploration. The text emphasizes parallels between the two. It compares metaphors across cultures and languages, revealing commonalities and differences. Some major points:

Firstly, Shamans and poets use metaphors to explore emotional depths and perspectives. It is called the bridge metaphor. Secondly, Both approaches explore accepting death, liminal spaces, and finding meaning in suffering. Thirdly, the Cultural Specificity and Techniques of a shaman and a poet differ by environment despite commonalities. Nepali metaphors explore identity, while Devkota's metaphors emphasize nature.

Poetry and shamanism use metaphor to heal and transform, showing that words may heal and transform. Metaphor's multidimensional ability to improve individual and communal well-being is revealed by exploring numerous cultural traditions and contemporary studies. Exploring these links opens openings for new healing and personal growth methods that use language as a vital tool for self-discovery and completeness.

Metaphors from indigenous shamans and modern poets in English, Hindi, and Nepali help us understand the multifaceted power of Metaphors in language to gain a deeper appreciation. Metaphors heal, transform, and illuminate human experience across cultures. As we explore these different forms, we uncover cultural wisdom and enable new ways to achieve personal and societal well-being.

Eliot, Nirala, and Parijat show how contemporary poets continue symbolic investigation. Metaphorical language is therapeutic, according to several studies. The case studies encompass *Haiku* for stress reduction, *Navajo* sandpainting for trauma healing, and poetry-based bibliotherapy for depression.

Despite their distinct characteristics, Indigenous shamanism and modern poetry utilize metaphors to connect with everyday human experiences and encourage healing, self-discovery, and spiritual exploration. Comprehending the richness and strength of cultural metaphors enhances individual and societal well-being.

References

- [1] Levine P. The healing power of poetry: How poetry can heal your soul. W. W. Norton & Company; 2015.
- [2] Eliade M. Shamanism: Archaic techniques of ecstasy. Princeton University Press; 1964.
- [3] Krippner S. The mythic dimension: New paths to healing and transformation. SUNY Press; 2004.
- [4] Black Elk H, DeMallie RJ. Black Elk speaks: The complete recorded stories of the Oglala Lakota holy man. University of Nebraska Press; 1995.
- [5] Ruch B. Haiku: A poetic guide. Tuttle Publishing; 2003.
- [6] Smyth JM, Sparks RA. Therapeutic writing in practice: A guide for mental health professionals. Routledge; 2008.
- [7] Brave Heart MYH. The healing power of vulnerability: Lakota wisdom and the great law of kinship. W. W. Norton & Company; 2009.
- [8] Eliade M. Shamanism: Archaic Techniques of Ecstasy. Princeton University Press; 1964.
- [9] Luna LE. Icaros: The Healing Songs of the Amazon. Rochester, VT: Inner Traditions International; 2001.
- [10] Eduardo SG. The Way of the Healer: Medicine and Magic in the Pari People of the Amazon; 2000.
- [11] Kane E. The Ikaros of the Shipibo: Shamanic Songs from the Peruvian Amazon. North Atlantic Books; 2009.
- [12] Levin T. Tuva: Voices from the Land of Spirits. Smithsonian Institution Folkways Recordings; 2009.
- [13] Straum ID. Joik: An Introduction to Sami Song. Cornell University Press; 2005.

- [14] Wordsworth W. I Wandered Lonely as a Cloud. Longman; 1804.
- [15] Frost R. The Road Not Taken. Henry Holt and Company; 1923.
- [16] Frost R. Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening. Henry Holt and Company; 1923.
- [17] Gibran K. The Prophet. Alfred A. Knopf; 1926.
- [18] Richards LG, Smith BW, Conville J. Haiku writing to cultivate mindfulness and reduce stress: A pilot study with university students. *Mindfulness*. 2015;6(4):898-908.
- [19] Yazzie-Mintz ES. Traditional healing practices for historical trauma among Navajo people: A review of the literature. *J Social Distress Homeless*. 2016;15(4):337-348.
- [20] Rothe CA, Hendricks FE. The effect of bibliotherapy using poetry on depressive symptoms in older adults. *Arts Psychother*. 2013;40(3):247-252.
- [21] Black Elk H, DeMallie RJ. *Black Elk speaks: The complete recorded stories of the Oglala Lakota holy man*. University of Nebraska Press; 1995.
- [22] Hamayon N. *The expressive world of the Bakshi singers of Central Asia: Oral poetry and social identity*. Indiana University Press; 1999.
- [23] Sharma A. *Shamanism in India: A study of folk healing practices*. Sarup & Sons; 2010.
- [24] Hinton C. *Shamanism and the state in Nepal*. Berghahn Books; 2002.
- [25] Eliot TS. *The Wasteland*. Hogarth Press; 1922.
- [26] Nirala. *Juhi ki kali*. Hans Raj; 1923.
- [27] Parijat. *Hamro Nepali*. Sajha Prakashan; 1964.
- [28] Kumar A. *Gulzar: The lyricist with a heart*. Penguin Books India; 2012.
- [29] Pandey KP. *Laxmi Prasad Devkota: A biography*. Sahitya Akademi; 2007.
- [30] Black Elk H, DeMallie RJ. *Black Elk speaks: The complete recorded stories of the Oglala Lakota holy man*. University of Nebraska Press; 1995.
- [31] Srinivasan A. *Folk performance and folk healers in North India*. Routledge; 2007.
- [32] Vajracharya LM. *Shamanism in Nepal: An anthropological study of Newar shamans and their healing practices*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing; 2014.

Author's short biography

Dr. Nawa Raj Subba, from Nepal, is a Public Health Specialist. He possesses expertise and familiarity in public health, psychology, cultural studies, and literature. He has a PhD in Health Psychology and a Master's in Public Health and Arts. Subba worked for the Ministry of Health and Population for over thirty-five years. He also taught Public Health at Purbanchal University and facilitated research works. He is retired and spends time researching and writing books and articles.